

UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF CORPUS-BASED APPROACH FOR LANGUAGE LEARNING

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The introduction of technology has caused a paradigm shift in language instruction, with the corpus-based method leading the way in this change. Learning a language has traditionally been focused on textbooks and planned activities that are frequently disconnected from the fluidity of language use in everyday situations. On the other hand, the corpus-based method provides a dynamic and real way to close the gap between classroom instruction and the complexities of real-world language communication.

Fundamentally, the corpus-based approach uses vast assemblages of real language data, or corpora, to guide and improve language teaching. This paper examines the many facets of the corpus-based approach as a pedagogic tool in language learning, highlighting its advantages and consequences for both teachers and students.

The capacity of the corpus-based method to expose students to genuine language in context is what gives it its didactic potential. Learners can understand the subtleties of language use in different communication contexts in addition to the formal rules of grammar and vocabulary by using real language usage from a variety of sources.

Further improving the field of pedagogical education, mastering foreign languages, having the skills to apply modern knowledge and pedagogical technologies, introducing advanced educational technologies to the field, making a worthy contribution to the socio-economic improvement of our country tasks such as training of qualified specialists are defined [1]. One of the important and most popular directions of applying information and communication technologies to educational processes is corpus linguistics or data-driven learning - DDL (data-driven learning) [2]. The ever-evolving professional communication landscape requires English for Special Purposes (ESP) learners to develop not only linguistic skills, but also strong communicative competencies (linguistic, pragmatic, sociolinguistic, and strategic) in their chosen field. To meet this need, English as a non-philological education (ESP) teachers are increasingly exploring innovative approaches, and the corpus-based approach is emerging as a promising tool. This article reveals the didactic possibilities of using corpus data, proposing a data-based approach to improving the communicative competence of non-philological education (ESP) students.

It examines the important role of professional communicative competence in empowering non-philological education (ESP) students in their professional contexts and the main principles of the corpus-based approach and interprets how it uses the wealth of authentic (original and authentic) information found in the corpus.

A number of scientists have conducted scientific research on the corpus. According to R. Reppen [3], "a corpus is a large, principled collection of electronically stored written or spoken texts that occur naturally."

Corpora is the plural form of corpus, a feature of corpora that helps identify "linguistic and situational examples" and provides a natural, original, ready-made source of language texts [4].

Using corpora with corpus-based learning technology (DDL-data-driven learning) requires the use of the following approaches: word lists, concordance lines. When searching for z, the line that comes with the searched words are called concordance lines)that includes highlighted texts and language registers (Fig. 1).

A corpus is a large, principally electronic collection of naturally occurring language samples [5]. A corpus is made by collecting a large number of written texts or records of spoken words. These texts or records are such as books, newspapers, and conversations. The collected language examples are then placed in a computer database (sketchengine). [7]. Using the corpus, students can build a vocabulary of professional terms related to their profession and explore the different translations and uses of these terms in different contexts [8]. This allows them to understand how language is adapted and used in specific domains [9]. In addition, corpora help students develop pragmatic skills by introducing them to real-life language use and the social and cultural context of communication [10]. By analyzing the examples of language units and communicative functions in the corpus, students can learn to write reports and use them effectively in different situations.

Corpus-based approach is one of the important factors in improving the professional communicative competence of non-philology students.

A corpus-based approach is a methodology that uses large collections of texts, known as corpora, to analyze and study different language phenomena. It involves extracting data from corpora and using them for research and analysis. This approach can be applied to a variety of fields, such as language learning and teaching, deriving semantic class analysis, music analysis and composition, and the study of individual variation in language use and the construction of dictionaries [12] Corpus-based approaches often include statistical analysis, connection models, and evolutionary components for insight and prediction. They serve as a resource for researchers and practitioners to study language patterns, identify trends, and make decisions based on empirical evidence.

Corpus-based learning refers to the use of corpora, which are databases containing texts, as a tool for language learning and teaching [17]. It involves the use of corpora to analyze language use, identify language instances, and study linguistic phenomena.

The didactic possibilities of the corpus-based approach to the development of professional communicative competences are wide and can cover various aspects of teaching.

The main didactic possibilities of the corpus-based approach

1. Learning professional terms and phraseology:	Corpus analysis allows students to study specific vocabulary and phraseology used in a professional field. Identify words and phrases that are often used in the context of professional activities.
2. Understanding the context of use:	Students can learn how certain terms or phrases are used in different professional contexts. Understanding context-based nuances enriches one's understanding of language.
3. Developing writing skills:	Analyzing texts from a corpus helps students learn about the different writing styles adopted in their professional fields. Developing professional writing skills.
4. Formation of translation competence:	Corpus translation helps students develop their translation skills in the context of their profession. Translation of texts taking into account the peculiarities of the field.
5. Analysis of information about the profession:	Studying professional scenarios in the corpus helps students prepare for typical communication situations in their field.
6. Training on cultural aspects:	Corpus-based training can include learning the characteristics of language and communicative culture in a professional context. To develop the skills of effective cooperation in an intercultural environment.
7. Individualization of training:	Students can use the corpus to personalize their studies by focusing on areas that best match their professional interests.
8. Automating the learning process:	The use of digital learning and artificial intelligence technologies in corpus-based learning facilitates the automation of the learning process by providing students with materials and feedback on their professional activities.

In conclusion, these didactic tools and corpus-based exercises (ESP) help to develop ESP students' language skills and speaking competence in their professional context.

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